

D2.4

Final version of the training platform and modules sustainability plan

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The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AAI	Authorization Infrastructure Architecture
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
D	Deliverable
D&E	Dissemination & Exploitation
DMP	Data Management Plan
E2E	End-to-end
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETHRD-IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data - Interest Group
GNI	Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LMS	Learning Management System
M	Month
NCP	National Contact Point
NOADs	National Open Access Desks
OA	Open Access
OER	Open Educational Resources
ORRI	Open and Responsible Research and Innovation
PBL	Project-Based Learning
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
T	Task
TtT	Train-the-Trainer
WP	Work Package

List of project participants

Short name	Legal name
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
AU	Aarhus Universitet
LOBA	GLOBAZ, S.A.
ESF	Fondation Europeenne de la Science
ZSI	Zentrum Fur Soziale Innovation GMBH
SISSA	Scuola Internazionale Superiore di Studi Avanzati di Trieste
LPI	Learning Planet Institute
OpenAIRE	OpenAIRE AMKE
UHelsinki	Helsingin Yliopisto
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
IZTECH	Izmir Institute of Technology
UDebrecen	Debreceni Egyetem
HEAL-Link	Panepistimio Patron
EARMA	European Association of Research Managers and Administrators
UniSR	Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele
DANS	Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie Van Wetenschappen - KNAW
RBI	Ruđer Bošković Institute
SciLink	Stichting SciLink
Uminho	Universidade do Minho

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Executive Summary

This report (D2.4) finalises the sustainability plan for PATTERN's training platform and modules, building on the preliminary conclusions of D2.3 (2025). It does not restate that framework but updates it on one decisive point. The question left open in D2.3, whether partner institutions would contribute financially after the project, has now been answered: partners wish to continue using the platforms and building on the pedagogical resources, but will not commit dedicated budgets once PATTERN ends.

This does not put sustainability at risk. OpenAIRE funds and maintains OpenPlato through a standing institutional commitment, and LPI has secured new grants and partnerships that keep the Projects platform open and developing. Both organisations are committed to maintaining the platforms for years to come. However, if organisations outside the consortium want to use the system, they will need to agree on a payment model.

The remainder of this report sets out how this is achieved: technical and financial sustainability of the platforms (Section 2), maintenance of the eight training courses through decentralised thematic stewardship (Section 3), and institutional integration (Section 4 and, in depth, D4.3). As in D2.3, the plan acknowledges the standing challenges — long-term funding, technological relevance, content currency, and Europe's diverse institutional landscape — and addresses them through diversified funding, modular and flexible approaches, and strong partnerships.

Notice that this report is highly similar to D2.3, since the foundational sustainability analysis at the basis of D2.3 has not changed (see chapter 6 for additional information). The key insight provided by this report is that **both digital platforms (for courses and for project-based learning) will stay open for at least five years after the PATTERN project ends, and the pedagogical resources will remain available to all interested learners and researchers.**

1 Introduction

This deliverable covers the area of training platform and modules sustainability. The elements that require sustainability consideration include the PATTERN Digital Ecosystem, which is made of three parts: (1) PATTERN website, (2) courses that are stored on OpenPlato (a Moodle learning content management system owned and run by OpenAIRE), (3) Projects (a project-based learning system owned and run by Learning Planet Institute). An integrated login system links OpenPlato and Projects. For these systems, there are two interdependent aspects – first, technical sustainability (making sure that the software will continue to run in the next 5 years); and financial sustainability (ensuring that the costs of running the system, such as hosting and the time for maintenance) are covered.

Secondly, partners looked at the eight courses that are developed and tested in PATTERN. For each of them, they have been considering how to maintain the courses up to date over the coming five years. This includes ensuring that the content remains relevant and current, and that the case studies that are used in the problem-based learning activities are relevant to the learning objectives.

Thirdly, partners looked at the organisational and institutional aspects that are relevant of the sustainability. The organisational aspects influence the sustainability because they will impact the way that the courses are integrated within institutions.

The effort to define and analyse the aspects of sustainability started in D2.3. In the year that passed since the deliverable was completed, the analysis proved robust and reflective of the consortium plans towards long term sustainability. The analysis from D2.3 shaped the effort of the consortium and the plans towards the end of the project. Because of this aspect, this deliverable should be considered as an updated version of D2.3, In Section 6, you will find details of the main areas of updates within this version. We have included the text of D2.3 to make the document readable without the need to refer to the deliverable while reading it.

1.1 Methodology

The information that is used in this report came from internal reviews of WP2 contributors. During year 2 of the project, the consortium agreed that WP2 and WP3 warrant a dedicated weekly meeting to ensure coordination and progression. These one-hour meetings provided an ongoing information exchange, with partners sharing the development and implementation of PATTERN elements – in particular courses and the digital environment – with WP2 and WP3 leading teams. As a result of these discussions, issues that are important for the sustainability of the project's outputs emerged and were captured. Following this, dedicated sessions during the second and third Open Studio cycle were devoted to the sustainability strategy. Prior to the third Open Studio cycle, all partners had to fill in an online consultation about key aspects of the long-term sustainability. Key relevant aspects are shared here.

The platforms usage Key Performance Indicators (KPI) information is extracted directly from the system logs or from specialized analytics tools such as Mixpanel, which analyze online usage.

1.2 Levels of sustainability

A key consideration in PATTERN is sustainability – ensuring that the project's outputs remain useful and accessible over time. This approach is applied to both the online technology platforms created by the project and the courses it offers, each with three defined levels of sustainability.

1.2.1 Sustainability of Technology Platforms

For the technology platforms developed in PATTERN (such as online learning portals or resource repositories), three levels of sustainability are considered:

Static Content Preservation: At the basic level, the platform's content (e.g. project documents, learning materials, and static resources) remains accessible even after the project ends. In this static state, all the valuable information and documents are preserved online for reference, ensuring nothing is lost even if no new activity occurs on the platform.

Active Use and Engagement: The second level ensures that new students, teachers, and researchers can continue to use and interact with the platform. In this sustained operational phase, the platform stays live and open to fresh users, allowing future cohorts to benefit from its tools and materials. Learners and instructors can engage with the content (and even contribute feedback or minor updates), keeping the platform active and relevant for a growing user base.

Continuous Improvement and Growth: The highest sustainability level involves ongoing development and expansion of the platform. Here, the platform not only remains active, but it is also regularly updated with new features, improvements, or content enhancements. Over time, the platform reaches an ever-growing audience beyond the initial target group, extending its impact. This means the platform evolves based on user needs and technological advancements, continuously improving while attracting more users.

1.2.2 Sustainability of Courses

Similarly, the courses and training programs offered through PATTERN have three parallel levels of sustainability:

Open and Accessible Course Materials: At the basic level, all course materials (lecture notes, slides, readings, tutorials, etc.) remain available as a long-term resource. Even after a course session has concluded, these materials are kept online or in repositories in OpenPlato, Projects and Zenodo, so that past participants and other interested learners can access them for reference. This ensures the knowledge disseminated by the course stays accessible and can continue to inform or guide research practice.

Ensuring the sustainability of PATTERN's training materials is essential. Static resources like PDFs will be archived on Zenodo, which provides DOIs for better

citation, attribution, and alignment with FAIR and Open Science principles. To enhance visibility, outputs should also be integrated into platforms such as EOSC, OpenAIRE, and UNESCO repositories. Clear metadata, authorship, and version control are key to avoiding content fragmentation. While Zenodo offers long-term preservation, dynamic courses will be hosted on platforms like OpenPlato, ensuring continued accessibility beyond the project's end.

Reuse, Re-run of Courses and Train the Trainers Module: The second level focuses on extending the life of the course by developing guidelines for re-use, making templates available and offering it again or adapting material for new groups. In PATTERN, courses can be reused or re-run in the future, enabling new learners to enrol and new instructors to teach the content. By re-running courses (or integrating the materials into other training programs), the project allows successive cohorts to benefit from the training without needing to develop new courses from scratch. This reusability demonstrates an active ongoing value of the course content. In parallel, self-paced *train the trainers* modules will provide methodological and didactic training for trainers to get insight not just on the content but on ways how these courses have been adapted and developed for PATTERN target audiences. D 2.1. covers all main aspects in all eight thematic areas around training methodology and learning paths developed to serve audience needs.

Continuous Update and Expansion: At the highest level, the course content and delivery are continuously updated, expanded, and scaled up. The curriculum is regularly refined based on participant feedback and new developments in ORRI, keeping the training up-to-date and improving its quality. Additionally, the course is offered to an increasing number of participants – for example, by opening it to other institutions or offering more frequent sessions. This continuous enhancement and broader outreach ensure the course remains current, grows in scope, and has a wider impact over time.

1.2.3 Pedagogical innovation sustainability

In addition to the other aspects of sustainability, the PATTERN courses also involve the use of multiple channels for engagement and for the reuse of training material (ex. flipped classrooms, hybrid sessions, gamification, etc.). In both training platforms that are used in PATTERN there is a scope for a teachers' forum as well as sharing teachers' comments and guidelines on Projects. In this way, the project can share the pedagogical innovations that were used to teach a specific element and allow other teachers to develop them further or add their own approach to the teaching.

2 Technical sustainability

2.1 Introduction to technical sustainability

As stated in the introduction, PATTERN's digital ecosystem consists of three main platforms:

- A general static web site that explains the project's philosophy and guides learners and teachers towards relevant resources.
- The [Projects platform](#), dedicated to learners' activities, centred on project-based learning (PBL) and use cases.
- The OpenPlato [platform](#), a Moodle learning management system (LMS) hosting pedagogical resources for teachers who want to implement ORRI in their courses.

Ensuring the continued operation of each of these components involves maintaining the underlying codebases, infrastructure, and interoperability between platforms, as well as securing commitments from hosting institutions to provide basic maintenance and updates beyond the end of the PATTERN grant.

2.2 PATTERN website

The PATTERN Website is an information, mostly static web site powered by a WordPress, a web content management system. As this technology is widely used, it is easy to maintain and does not necessitate large resources nor deep technical expertise to maintain, even after the end of the PATTERN grant. However, technical security updates will be needed to prevent malicious attacks, such as defacing or security breaches. LOBA will stay responsible for the web site maintenance and security for five years after the end of the project.

LOBA estimated the costs to be low, covering web site hosting, site maintenance and domain registration.

LOBA will keep online and maintain the PATTERN web site for 5 years after the end of the project.

2.3 PATTERN courses on OpenPlato

2.3.1 Description of technical sustainability and maintenance

OpenPlato is a Moodle-based LMS and training catalogue for Open Science, RDM, and FAIR principles, developed by OpenAIRE and aligned with EOSC policies. It is operated by the University of Warsaw's ICM, OpenAIRE, and OpenAIRE's Support and Training Standing Committee, and is financed and governed by OpenAIRE.

For sustainability, the key points are that OpenPlato relies on widely-used, interoperable standards (Moodle, SCORM, xAPI) and structured, FAIR-compliant metadata (based on RDA ETHRD-IG recommendations), which keep its content discoverable, reusable, and portable across institutional environments. Its "training

spaces" model and EOSC AAI integration further support reuse and institutional adoption.

2.3.2 OpenPlato's digital Ecosystem

OpenPlato is an established, actively-used infrastructure, not just a project deliverable. These figures span three scopes. At the widest level, OpenAIRE's training network (NOADs and affiliated trainers) has run 800+ events reaching 30,000+ learners with 1,200 trainers. Within that network, the OpenPlato platform itself hosts 59+ courses and 2,000+ active users, with more than 6.42 million site-wide interactions since launch. Most recently, the platform recorded 719 course enrolments and 54,605 course-level visits over the last two years. This existing scale and ongoing use by OpenAIRE, NOADs, and partner communities is itself the core of OpenPlato's sustainability: PATTERN's courses are embedded in a platform that already operates as long-term Training-as-a-Service, well beyond any single funding cycle.

2.3.3 Additional Tools for Digital Material production

OpenPlato's content production relies on tools and standards that support long-term reuse: third-party authoring tools (e.g. Articulate Rise 360), Moodle's embedded H5P, and compatibility with SCORM and xAPI. These let trainers convert existing materials (such as PowerPoint) into interactive, trackable, and portable courses with minimal additional work, which directly aids the reusability and maintainability of PATTERN's outputs.

Most importantly for sustainability, OpenPlato's governance model is backed by a dedicated annual financial commitment from OpenAIRE AMKE. This funding secures ongoing system upgrades, technical support, and user training, positioning OpenPlato as a maintained, future-proof component of the EOSC training landscape — independent of PATTERN project funding.

2.3.4 Hosting and Maintenance by Third Parties

OpenPlato is hosted in a secure, EU-compliant European data centre, with infrastructure managed by a trusted institutional partner and platform updates, security patches, and bug fixes handled by third-party providers specialising in open-source educational technology. These long-term service agreements guarantee operational continuity within the EOSC and OpenAIRE ecosystem.

Content sustainability follows a decentralised model in which course authors and thematic leads own updates to their materials, supported by an expert editorial board overseeing quality and EU-framework alignment. A full mapping of PATTERN training materials (PowerPoints, PDFs, external tools) has been completed to aid version control. Authors are responsible for routine content audits, fixing outdated references and broken links, and documenting and licensing external tools; a sustainability framework currently in development will formalise these practices. Maintenance effort is scaled to need, as foundational materials require little, while interactive or

tool-based modules need more frequent revision. Reuse is supported at both levels: metadata is released under CC0, while course-content reuse follows the permissions set by each resource provider.

2.3.5 PATTERN Open Studio Outcomes: Advancing OpenPlato's Sustainability

The PATTERN Open Studios (Braga, the two online cycles, and Brussels, organised by ESF under WP4) examined OpenPlato's sustainability across pedagogical, technical, and financial dimensions. The financial question, left open in D2.3, has since been resolved and is summarised below; the technical risks and mitigations are addressed in 2.6.

2.3.6 Financial Sustainability and Institutional Buy-In

The Open Studios confirmed that universities, which largely run their own LMS, are reluctant to fund a platform they perceive as duplicative. The conclusion is therefore straightforward: OpenPlato does not depend on financial contributions from PATTERN partners. It is centrally maintained and funded by OpenAIRE through a dedicated annual commitment from OpenAIRE AMKE (see 2.3.3), and its financial base rests on continued use within EU-funded projects and the EOSC EU Node ecosystem, where it anchors service tutorials, onboarding, and reusable training pathways. A range of complementary funding models was explored during the Open Studios (voluntary subscriptions or sponsorships, crowdfunding, an "Open Library of Humanities"-style model where a few institutions underwrite open access for all, and co-development partnerships via the NOADs network). These remain available as optional ways to diversify support, but none is required to keep OpenPlato open.

2.4 PATTERN Projects

2.4.1 Key Features of the PATTERN Projects Platform

The PATTERN Projects platform supports collaborative, project-based learning tailored to Open RRI, with key features designed to empower both learners and educators:

- Customizable project templates that help teachers guide learners in structuring goals, documenting progress, and reflecting on outcomes.
- Mentor matching and peer supervision tools to support learning through guided collaboration.
- AI-powered recommendations to connect users with relevant projects, peers, and mentors.
- Geolocation features to map activities and promote local collaboration.
- Integrated notifications to keep users informed of updates, feedback, and milestones.
- Digital portfolios aligned with the SDGs to highlight individual and collective impact.

Hosted securely on EU-compliant Azure servers in France, the platform supports data protection and technical sustainability for the PATTERN learning community.

2.4.2 An open-source strategy to improve sustainability

The PATTERN Projects platform is a specific instance of PROJECTS, an open-source¹ web platform created by Learning Planet Institute. It is released under a creative commons licence (CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0).

By being open-source, the platform ensures that its code is transparent, adaptable, and continuously improved by a global community of developers. This collaborative approach enables long-term technical sustainability, as the platform can evolve without being tied to proprietary systems or vendor lock-in. Additionally, the platform's release under the Creative Commons (CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0) license ensures that it remains freely available for non-commercial use and can be modified or shared, promoting its use in diverse educational contexts and ensuring its accessibility for years to come.

Partners chose this specific non-commercial license for the PATTERN Projects platform to ensure its accessibility to educational and non-profit users. At the same time, this license allows us to generate revenue by offering the platform as a SaaS or licensing it to commercial entities, ensuring the platform's financial sustainability without compromising its core mission of open access.

2.4.3 Technical architecture

The technical stack leverages modern web technologies across multiple layers:

- **Frontend:** Vue.js
- **Backend:** Python, Django, Celery, Redis
- **Authentication & Security:** Keycloak
- **Search & Indexing:** OpenSearch
- **Storage:** Azure Blob Storage, PostgreSQL
- **Real-time Collaboration:** Hocus Pocus
- **Maps:** OpenStreetMap
- **AI Integration:** Mistral AI
- **Analytics & Monitoring:** Mixpanel
- **Testing & QA:** Playwright (for end-to-end testing)

Most of these technologies are open-source, but LPI is also leveraging commercial services: Mixpanel for analytics, Microsoft Azure for hosting and Mistral Artificial Intelligence (AI) for text summarization and content recommendations (commercial offering, though based on open models).

All these technologies are widely used and chosen for their ease of maintenance.

¹ Source code and technical documentation: <https://github.com/CyberCRI/projects-frontend>

By primarily relying on state-of-the-art open-source technologies, partners ensure the long-term sustainability of their tech stack.

2.4.4 Platform hosting

The PATTERN projects platform is hosted on Microsoft Azure servers located in France, ensuring compliance with EU data protection regulations and providing a secure, high-availability environment. This setup supports technical sustainability through robust performance, data integrity, and disaster recovery capabilities. The platform is built using Kubernetes container orchestration technology, which allows for seamless portability. This architecture ensures that, if needed, the platform can be migrated to another cloud provider with minimal disruption, preserving continuity and flexibility over the long term.

2.4.5 Long term maintenance, safety and security

For long-term maintenance, safety, and security, LPI prioritizes robust development practices to ensure the platform's reliability and protection. LPI implements unit testing and end-to-end (E2E) testing to catch bugs early and maintain high-quality code, ensuring the platform performs as expected in real-world scenarios. Additionally, LPI focuses on security best practices by regularly updating dependencies, conducting security audits, and applying necessary patches. The development process follows an iterative agile approach, with two-week sprints to ensure continuous improvement and quick adaptation to new needs or issues. This collaborative and agile approach not only strengthens the platform's security and performance over time but also fosters a long-term, community-driven commitment to its growth and stability. To ensure sustainable development, LPI actively engages with partner university developers, providing opportunities for them to contribute to the platform's evolution and maintenance.

2.4.6 Estimated costs

LPI has developed a preliminary estimate of the technical costs required to sustain the platform after the PATTERN grant ends, outlined across three scenarios. Small costs such as domain registration and online tools licences are aggregated under Servers & Cloud Services.

The three levels of platform usage are as follows:

1. Static projects and documents only
2. New students and teachers can still interact with the platforms
3. LPI's platforms keep improving with new features and reach a growing audience

	Servers & Cloud services	Technical support	Functional support	New features	Yearly Cost
Level 1	30k€ / year overall For PATTERN, 3k€/year	DevOps specialist 2% of his time for PATTERN	No support	None	3k€
Level 2	30k€ / year overall For PATTERN, 5k€/year	DevOps specialist 15% of his time for PATTERN	Junior employee 20% of her time	None	20k€
Level 3	30k€ / year overall For PATTERN, 8k€/year	DevOps specialist 25% of his time for PATTERN	Junior employee 50% of her time	Senior Full stack Developer 80k€	120k€

Figure 1 - Funding needs levels by domain for three levels of platform sustainability

2.4.7 Potential sources of funding

Potential solutions were explored during dedicated sessions of the second cycle of Open Studio in Braga, through participatory workshops.

Many ideas were explored to secure funding for the platforms, such as:

- Crowdfunding or offering courses
- Sponsorship opportunities
- Pilots may direct additional students to Projects after the project's conclusion, for a fee
- Leveraging the EOSC Node ecosystem
- Integrating the platform into curricula

It's important to note that universities are unlikely to invest significant amounts unless the **courses are integrated into their existing curriculum.**

To support long-term sustainability, participants suggested introducing membership models or access fees, supported by mutual agreements between partners to maintain the platforms post-project. Company sponsorships and a cooperative funding model, inspired by the Open Library of Humanities, were proposed—where many benefit but only some contribute financially. Expanding use beyond the PATTERN consortium could broaden support, and sponsoring specific trainings (e.g. with university logos) was seen as a practical, visible way to attract institutional backing.

The 2026 workshop in Brussels confirmed that most universities, many of which are facing financial difficulties, **will not invest significant money** to sustain the PATTERN project platform specifically.

Expanding progressively the partners with the support of new grants can improve the long-term sustainability, financially and technically long after the end of the grant. Several candidate grants have already been discussed.

However, the development of the project platform goes well beyond the PATTERN community. New partnerships with leading French Universities (in particular with Sorbonne University) have raised substantial amounts to sustain the platform and develop new functions, especially for research communities. A new ERASMUS+ citizen science project has also brought funding for new AI features. Several grants are pending, with good chances of success.

2.4.8 PROJECTS platform current roadmap

The PROJECTS platform development is already supported by several grants and partners, including a French national research funding agency (ANR) grant, a Regional Parisian grant, private foundations and several European universities outside the scope of the PATTERN project. As an open-source project, the future features development is prioritized with the help of all the research and pedagogical communities involved.

The key features of the Projects platform roadmap are:

- Advanced pedagogical AI assistants, supporting all major LLMs: September 2026
- Advanced Researcher profiles: December 2026
- Integration of OPENALEX science domains reference database: February 2027
- Conversational search and analysis features: June 2027

These features are already financed. Future grants will enable new open-source features, available to all communities.

All developments are shared with all Projects Platform partners. Some features financed by other partners will directly benefit the PATTERN community, such as flexible structure, AI extraction of researcher's skills and profiles, content editorialization and advanced search through natural language leveraging AI Large Language Models and Transformers.

Developments of new features are grouped in three main categories:

- Pedagogy: these features add value to educators and teachers or help learners build skills more efficiently. The development team will focus on advanced AI features such as AI mentoring and skills evaluation
- Research: the Projects platform will integrate open-source developments directly useful to researchers, such as skills AI extraction and analysis from publications and advanced research features.
- All: generic, multi-purpose features such as community animation, improved performances, scalability and security and easy data export.

2.5 PATTERN login and connection between Projects and OpenPlato

LPI and OpenAIRE partners have created a **common login system, integrating both platforms to streamline the user experience.**

2.5.1 Authentication system operation

Authentication is managed by the Projects platform, with accounts and passwords stored on Keycloak, a highly scalable open-source account management system. On OpenPlato, users can log in using their Projects credentials, which redirects them to a login page. If the user is new, they are directed to an account creation form. Once the account is created, single sign-on (SSO) is enabled across both platforms.

In summary, Projects acts as the identity provider, while OpenPlato serves as the service provider.

2.5.2 Estimated maintenance costs

Maintaining this service incurs minimal costs as long as both platforms remain technically supported. **Learning Planet Institute, LOBA and Open AIRE have committed to providing at least basic maintenance for the next five years.**

2.6 General overview of the technical sustainability

2.6.1 Who will maintain the platforms technically?

For both Projects and OpenPlato, internal teams (LPI Digital Team for Projects and OpenAIRE for OpenPlato) will assume technical responsibility. The PATTERN leaders have defined responsibilities, to ensure ongoing updates and platform security.

As stated before, LPI has defined 3 levels of accessibility of the platform (static data stays accessible, courses can still be followed, new content and classes can be added); the risks and costs rise with each level. The incurring cost rise with each level of the long-term ambition of their sustainability strategy.

A point raised during the Brussels Open Studio is that new users of the PATTERN Projects portal currently require administrator approval to register, which adds friction for newcomers. Self-service account creation is already a platform feature and simply needs to be activated on the PATTERN portal, removing this bottleneck and supporting the "active use" level of sustainability.

2.6.2 What are the long-term sustainability risks?

Identified risks include unclear long-term hosting plans, limited accessibility of platforms and content, and dependency on external tools or frameworks. Security risks will rise with time if the platforms are not maintained technically by IT experts. Data preservation and interoperability (especially between PATTERN platforms and others like EOSC) is critical. For OpenPlato, potential misalignment with other

initiatives or data models is seen as a threat by PATTERN pilots. Projects and OpenPlato internal teams will try to integrate PATTERN outputs into established open-access directories, like EOSC, and to foster a user and contributor community. Partners will explore creating national working groups, Git repositories for platform content, using ZENODO (which create a long-lasting DOI) and aligning with broader European infrastructure standards (e.g. OpenAIRE, FAIR) to promote sustainability and openness.

Creating a living open-source community to maintain and develop the code of Projects would be useful but a core technical team is needed, that will have to be funded.

The group emphasized the importance of making the platforms accessible, ensuring content longevity, and building networks of reuse (e.g. with other European projects and national initiatives). Interoperability, discoverability, and content reuse (e.g., via metadata standards) are important for ensuring long-term technical sustainability.

2.6.3 Platforms financial sustainability

Sustainability funding beyond the project lifecycle remains a key concern. Funding needs to be secured to maintain core platforms and website infrastructure for at least 5 years post-project. Partners will strive to create a network of members who pay a voluntary fee to sustain the platforms as their preferred strategy.

We estimate that the financial support for Projects will exceed 120k€ a year for at least two years, which will provide for the third level of sustainability support. In fact, a new grant of 151k€ over two years supporting the maintenance and development of new features for the Projects platform was won in June 2026; another grant of 100k€ from the French Research Ministry is in the final review stage.

Winning new grants to support the development of new features after the next 2 years is highly likely. Therefore, **we anticipate that level 3 support** (see figure on chapter 2.4.6) **will be covered for the Projects Platform, as well as level 2 for the website and the Open Plato platform.**

3 Courses sustainability

3.1 Introduction to courses sustainability

The sustainability of PATTERN training courses relies on a clear, flexible strategy that enables long-term use, local adaptation, and regular updates. From the start, courses are designed for reuse—using modular formats, open licensing, and train-the-trainer (TtT) materials to build institutional capacity.

A shared responsibility model supports content maintenance: local teams adapt and deliver training, the PATTERN core team ensures quality, and thematic partners update content in their areas of expertise (e.g. FAIR RDM, Open Access). To keep materials relevant, updates were made during the second learning cycle, aligned with evolving policies and research practices.

Good practices like using real-world case studies, flipped classrooms, and multimedia scenarios are embedded to boost engagement and adaptability. This combined approach ensures that PATTERN courses remain useful, usable, and up-to-date across institutions and over time.

A cross-cutting point from the Brussels Open Studio is that reuse of PATTERN materials is, in several themes, already happening ahead of any formal adoption. The main remaining step is therefore formalization. Partners agreed to ensure proper archiving before the project ends and to settle on a consistent CC-BY license with standard attribution wording and disclaimer crediting PATTERN (possibly translated into several languages)². To enable genuine adaptation, editable formats (e.g. .pptx) should be made available alongside .pdf versions.

3.1.1 Pedagogical Sustainability partners consultation results

The consultation that was run in April 2026 just before the third Open Studio in Brussels showed a willingness of the partners to keep updating the courses as long as possible.

² On this matter, see also PATTERN D5.5 Final Strategic Exploitation Plan

Figure 2 - Thematic leaders' willingness to keep updating material beyond the Grant duration

According to the 3rd Open Studio consultation in April 2026, Open Plato will be maintained and used after the end of PATTERN; however, most partners will not make major changes to their courses on this platform. Existing courses will stay available and communicated for relevant courses.

Figure 3 - Thematic leaders' willingness to keep using Open Plato beyond the Grant duration

One major change in the last year of the project is that Zenodo has been used to reference the most replicable and useful pedagogical resources. It provides a long-term pointer to these resources.

Figure 4 - Availability of resources on Zenodo community (April 2026)

Figure 5 - Thematic leaders' willingness to keep using Zenodo beyond the Grant duration

During the last Open Studio in Brussels, a collective decision was made to reference on Zenodo all major pedagogical resources.

The Projects platform is mostly useful when doing project-based learning activities, deeply embedded in the curriculum. Only 50% of the partners will continue animating new trainings on Projects after the end of PATTERN. A minority (12.5%) plan to create new activities and use cases and to further expand their interactive case-based courses.

Figure 6 - Thematic leaders' willingness to keep using Projects beyond the Grant duration

3.1.2 Pedagogical Sustainability and Integration in OpenPlato LMS

A central theme is the importance of interoperability with existing teaching systems. Participants emphasized the need for OpenPlato to align with institutional LMS and curricula, ensuring it supports structured learning pathways rather than functioning solely as a repository of self-paced content. Integration with EOSC's AAI was highlighted as a critical feature to enhance user accessibility and cross-platform interoperability.

The reusability of educational content emerged as another major concern. Stakeholders advocated for course materials to be made available in formats such as SCORM, PDF, and H5P—ensuring compatibility with other platforms and long-term usability. Hosting of materials on trusted repositories like Zenodo, with persistent identifiers and proper licensing, was seen as essential for maximizing discoverability and adherence to FAIR principles.

Suggestions to improve pedagogical support included:

- Translation of training materials to enhance accessibility across linguistic communities.
- Incorporation of structured case studies in modular and adaptable formats.
- Development of features such as student self-assessment, and tools to better support neurodiverse learners.
- Exploration of a chatbot to guide users in navigating OpenPlato content and broader PATTERN resources.

However, the sessions also raised concerns around the platform's current orientation toward asynchronous, self-paced learning. Usability testing and feedback loops were proposed to ensure OpenPlato evolves into a more comprehensive educational tool that could support hybrid or structured learning models.

3.2 Citizen Science

AU has developed two robust Citizen Science training modules grounded in a blended learning model. The content of each module includes two presentations and ten case study descriptions that support an engaging, 2-2.5 hour live format focused on introducing citizen science or community engagement and participatory research, respectively. In Cycle 1, AU successfully piloted flipped classroom sessions combining pre-distributed materials with active case-based discussions. In addition, Citizen science modules have been fully integrated into PATTERN's digital ecosystem through the e-learning platforms. More specifically on the Projects Platform, the 10 structured case studies were hosted and used as core study materials for PBL activities. Each case study guided learners in critically evaluating key aspects such as purpose, methods, participant engagement, ethical considerations, and outcomes. Additionally, in LC2, the developed modules were refined and adapted to new contexts, e.g., the Circle U Summer School, a municipality-based workshop in Denmark, and a joint citizen science seminar with UHEL, as well as a dedicated Train-the-Trainer guide linked to the existing topics was made [available on OpenPlato](#). To support continuous improvement, training analytics and evaluation tools were deployed (see D3.3³), tracking participant interactions and gathering feedback on engagement levels and content relevance.

3.2.1 Content maintenance

AU will maintain the Citizen Science materials and continue refining them through new pilots in diverse contexts. A TtT Guide is available to institutional facilitators. Rather than developing standalone self-paced modules, AU has embeded structured activities into OpenPlato and Projects, using a blended model that ensures engagement through live activation. Curriculum mapping has also highlighted how Citizen Science links with other themes like Science Communication and Research Integrity, promoting content reuse and skill transfer.

Beyond AU's stewardship, LPI is already using an adapted version of the Citizen Science training with external audiences, indicating active reuse of the materials beyond the consortium.

3.2.2 Case studies maintenance

Building on the success of case-based training in Cycle 1, AU expanded its set of Citizen Science study cases by incorporating examples tailored to the profiles of new participants. These cases serve as the foundation for group discussion and collaborative exercises within live and online workshops and Projects-based activities. All study cases will be reviewed regularly to ensure alignment with transferable competencies and thematic coherence across the PATTERN curriculum.

³ doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15209490

3.3 Science Communication

SISSA, with the support of RBI, has developed a 15-hour course on *Science Communication* consisting of five core modules covering a general introduction and four specific topics in line with Grant Agreement: media writing, interviews, social media and communication with policymakers. The content was designed for trainers, including for each module: a PowerPoint presentation, a script that could be used as a potential reference from trainers and full guidelines including description of the training and practical activities, schedule and bibliography. Examples are included in each presentation and can be customised by each trainer. Starting from this material an Articulate version (i.e. digital material course creator tool) of the material for trainers has been developed and is about to be finalised for upload on OpenPlato.

3.3.1 Content maintenance

SISSA, in partnership with AU, will lead the maintenance and further development of the Science Communication training content. Some updates have already been implemented since the first version of the material was released last fall (first pilot training event November 2024). The plan includes analysing the feedback from the evaluation collected, discussing potential changes to the material with other pilot institutions including a reduction of the number of modules. The possibility of transforming the selected content into self-paced modules for OpenPlato and the development of project-based activities for the Projects platform will also be discussed. A clearer division was made between trainer resources and learner-facing content.

SISSA is already delivering the PATTERN-developed Science Communication training to external audiences as part of its institutional role, and additional Science Communication materials will be made available on the Coalesce academy.

3.3.2 Case studies maintenance

The course has provided examples and case studies through the lectures. Moreover, students have been using their own research projects to practice different communication skills, from writing press releases to being interviewed, using social media or giving short talks. SISSA, together with AU and with the help of LPI and OpenAire, will explore the reuse of student-generated examples from Cycle 1 to create mini-projects and case-based learning content for the Projects platform. Drawing inspiration from the DANS' FAIR RDM model, SISSA will structure each study case with context, objectives, and engagement prompts. This transformation will not only enrich the learner experience but also contribute to the visibility of science communication as a core pillar within Open Scholarly Communication.

3.4 Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results

This training course has been developed by APRE and LOBA, with the support of three pilot organizations (UniSR, SISSA and IZTECH). It designed to enhance researchers' understanding of dissemination and exploitation (D&E) as essential components in maximising the impact of research projects. With a specific focus on Horizon Europe proposals and projects, the course equips participants with the tools and knowledge needed to develop effective communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) strategies. Through practical case studies and interactive learning based on real Horizon Europe proposal excerpts, learners are guided on how to increase project visibility, leverage social media, and pitch their research outcomes to broader audiences.

While the courses primarily target doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, they are also relevant for early-career researchers with an interest in D&E or active roles within funded research projects. Additionally, Research Managers and research support staff dealing with EU projects at any level (i.e. Universities' Grant Offices) might benefit from this training too.

3.4.1 Content maintenance

To ensure the sustainability of the training content beyond the lifetime of the project and, potentially, of Horizon Europe, APRE is currently revising and updating the course for the second learning cycle. This involves decoupling the core D&E concepts from Horizon Europe-specific regulations and language, making the course applicable and relevant in a broader and more durable context. Horizon Europe will continue to be used as a real-life scenario and a source of examples, but no longer as the sole framework structuring the content.

Furthermore, the course is being restructured to strengthen its modularity: four independent but complementary modules will allow flexible use, adaptation, and targeted updates.

Given APRE's institutional mission and extensive experience in European project design and training, including on D&E, future content updates can possibly be integrated as new FP10 emerge, ensuring continued relevance and applicability, while maintaining a strong and reliable framework of reference for all researchers within and beyond Europe.

As part of its institutional role, APRE already delivers D&E training to its members and has updated that training over the past two years drawing on the PATTERN version. With appropriate adjustments and proper reference to PATTERN, an updated version of the D&E training is likely to be offered as a paid-for training delivered by APRE, providing a revenue-supported route to long-term continuation.

3.4.2 Case studies maintenance

The current case studies are based on Horizon Europe proposals. These will be reviewed and updated by APRE as part of its routine work in project development and

support. As soon as the next EU Framework Programme becomes operational and begins producing relevant outcomes, the course's examples can be refreshed accordingly. This dynamic approach to content maintenance has the potential to ensure that case studies remain up to date and reflective of the evolving European R&I landscape.

3.5 Gender, Non-Discrimination and Inclusion

The GNI Course was developed by UniSR in its role as thematic lead, with contributions from ESF and LPI in the production, review, and adaptation of the course content. Additional support was provided by teachers from the Data and Gender Observatory, Z-Inspection, and FORRT.

During LCI, UniSR and LPI piloted an online synchronous course. Registration for the webinar was made available to both UniSR and external participants through the project platform, which also hosted the course materials. This course is mandatory for the Université Paris Cité-LPI MSc year 2 students and got the accreditation from the UP Cité with 3 ECTS.

Following the pilot phase, UniSR developed an asynchronous online course based on the previously tested materials. The course is structured into three modules and is hosted on the OpenPLATO platform. All materials produced, including presentations and guidelines, were also uploaded to the PATTERN Community on Zenodo and to the Project Platform.

3.5.1 Content maintenance

UniSR, as thematic leaders in the design and implementation of training courses on GNI, began by enriching the courses already integrated into their PhD educational offering. Building upon this foundation, UniSR expanded the courses to meet PATTERN objectives, while ensuring they remained relevant and impactful for PhD students.

The sustainability of the GNI training courses beyond the first learning cycle and possibly beyond PATTERN's lifespan, will be guaranteed through their continued integration into the UniSR doctoral training offer. These courses will undergo regular review, updating and approval processes. By so doing, the enhanced GNI training modules will remain highly valuable not only for PhD students but also for the broader PATTERN scientific community, remaining aligned with evolving academic needs and maintaining relevance.

Building on LPI's experience of granting ECTS credits for the GNI course, other pilot institutions (e.g. UniSR) are considering similar recognition. ECTS accreditation is seen as a practical lever both for securing participant recruitment and for justifying the continued updating of content. To be durable, such recognition — particularly for mandatory courses at PhD level — benefits from support at institutional policy level, embedding the courses within institutions' strategic priorities and facilitating their integration into the curricula.

3.5.2 Case studies maintenance

The case studies developed by UniSR have been designed to be integrated effectively into the core content of the GNI training modules. Consequently, they will be subject to the same evaluation and approval process, ensuring their continued relevance and keeping them up to date.

3.6 Mental Health & Leadership

SciLink has developed a modular training series on *Mental Health Leadership* tailored to early career researchers, focusing on emotional resilience, leadership development, mentor-mentee relationships, and academic networking. The training adopts a flipped classroom approach and includes both in-person and online components. Twelve webinars are planned, open to REMO audiences, and all sessions will be recorded and shared as Open Educational Resources (OER) via OpenPlato and the PATTERN platform. Training content is enriched with participant-submitted scenarios to stimulate reflective, problem-based learning.

3.6.1 Content maintenance

SciLink will take the lead in maintaining and continuously updating the Mental Health Leadership training materials. Trainers are expected to refine their modules based on post-session feedback and evolving needs from participants. A shared responsibility model will be implemented, where SciLink manages the thematic content, the central PATTERN team oversees pedagogical alignment and platform integration, and partner organizations may contribute localized examples or translations. Updates will be tracked through the Projects platform and coordinated via admin access and structured feedback loops.

3.6.2 Case studies maintenance

SciLink will integrate anonymized, real-life study cases gathered through structured pre-training submissions from participants. These cases will be used to initiate discussion in both webinars and face-to-face trainings. Each case will be linked to a sub-project within the Projects platform, enabling ongoing peer reflection and collaborative commentary. This ensures that the training remains grounded in authentic challenges and supports context-specific learning—particularly around leadership dilemmas, academic isolation, and team communication in mental health-sensitive research environments.

3.7 Open Access

UMinho, jointly with OpenAIRE, HEAL-Link, UDebrecen, Iztech and RBI, have developed a comprehensive set of courses to promote Open Access (OA) topic and cover the gaps identified, mapped and assessed previously in WP1. This resulted in 4 courses: 1) Open Access publishing: overcoming the challenges and busting the myths (2h self-paced course); 2) Trusted publishers for my research: decoding good practices and overcoming predatory publishers (2h face-to-face); 3) Empowering researchers: retaining copyright and maximizing your impact in Open Access Publishing (1h30 webinar or 2h face to face session) ; 4) Meeting funder requirements: navigating Open Access Publishing (2h face-to-face). The courses have been designed in co-creation with the pilot institutions and the results from the first testing phase have been reflected to improve the final content. Also, a very flexible approach has been adopted, allowing for selection of different delivery modes (e.g. the Empowering researchers course can either be a webinar or a face-to-face session), translations to the pilot institution's languages, and incorporation of regional/ national content (e.g., national laws). Alongside the set of materials, there is also guidance for trainers on how to customize and deliver each course.

3.7.1 Content maintenance

UMinho lead the ongoing development and necessary updates of both the self-paced courses and the guidance for trainers. This maintenance was carried out within the scope of the OpenPlato platform's course portfolio under the supervision of the OpenPlato editorial team. All the course materials were created using reliable tools and considering the sustainability of the content itself, in order to require minimal updating needs.

As a leading OpenAIRE training partner, UMinho is committed to the continuous improvement and relevance of these educational resources. This commitment includes regular reviews and updates of course content, the incorporation of feedback from trainers and trainees, and alignment with emerging best practices in Open Science training and research.

Updates to the OA materials on OpenPlato follow a defined editorial lifecycle: the OpenPlato editorial team periodically contacts module authors to request updates, and content that is no longer maintained is archived. UMinho will additionally promote the materials through its internal university channels and continue reusing content from the OA bootcamp, with a system in place to track this reuse. On Zenodo, all OA materials remain freely available with authors and contributors clearly listed, and versioning is used to keep track of updates; the consortium is also considering adding further owners to the PATTERN Zenodo community so that contributors can upload material individually.

3.7.2 Case studies maintenance

UMinho, in collaboration with OpenAIRE, will oversee the maintenance and ongoing updating of the case studies developed within the Open Access courses. This effort will

be supported by contributions from OpenAIRE AMKE member organizations that are actively involved in the Training and Support Standing Committee and related working groups.

The maintenance strategy is integrated into OpenAIRE's internal organizational structure, drawing on the expertise of the OpenPlato editorial team and the Training and Support SC. This collaborative approach ensures that the case studies remain current, relevant and aligned with the evolving practices and needs of the Open Science community.

3.8 FAIR Research Data Management

DANS has developed a comprehensive, modular training suite on FAIR RDM, consisting of five core sessions (2.5 hours each) delivered face-to-face. Each session includes multiple PowerPoint presentations, exercises, and a TtT component, along with a pre-course document and a set of eight PBL assignments. Additionally, two self-paced courses, one of sessions 1-3 and the other of sessions 4-5, designed by DANS, have been launched offering a condensed digital entry point. The full course suite is complemented by recorded sessions, gamified elements, and practical Data Management Plan (DMP) exercises, that can be combined with local DMP writing tools, or with others such as ARGOS which is supported by OpenAIRE's team. In current versions, the Projects e-learning platform hosts two versions of FAIR RDM digital training material one for learners and one for other Trainers TtT. Both versions include downloadable material in edible versions.

3.8.1 Content maintenance

DANS led the continued development of the self-paced course series, to convert all five sessions into accessible e-learning modules. These modules are hosted on OpenPlato and support flipped learning models, enabling learners to engage with materials before participating in live workshops or bootcamps. OpenAIRE will ensure alignment with KPIs, integrating these courses into future the Train-the-Trainer bootcamps and Data Steward Bootcamp. To address known access issues and engagement gaps, the team will enhance platform interoperability, offer editable Articulate files for local reuse, and establish feedback loops for continuous improvement.

The FAIR RDM materials are sustained across three storage locations — Zenodo, OpenPlato, and the Projects platform — and keeping them current is understood as a shared, collaborative responsibility. One idea raised was that the former consortium might meet periodically, for instance through an occasional roundtable, to discuss continued engagement. Sustainability is further supported by the fact that FAIR RDM competency profiles are already reflected in the national curriculum for data stewards in the Netherlands. To aid discoverability, theme keywords could also be made findable through general web search.

3.8.2 Case studies maintenance

Study cases are central to the FAIR RDM approach, with DANS & OpenAIRE plus affiliates network jointly curating a diverse set of project-based assignments focused on realistic research scenarios. These cases cover data sharing, licensing, and privacy challenges, and are used in both self-paced modules and in interactive breakout discussions. Participants are encouraged to engage with these scenarios, for instance via the Projects platform, where they provide reflections and complete DMP exercises collaboratively. Feedback and comments collected during pilot use can be transformed into new study cases or integrated into gamified elements such as quizzes and peer-review tasks. Future iterations will emphasize cultural adaptability and modularity to serve both researchers and data professionals across contexts.

3.9 Research Integrity

The Research Integrity module, conceptualised and produced by EARMA and led by AU and UniSR, is built on a foundational set of five structured PowerPoint presentations covering key concepts in responsible research and innovation, including good scientific practices and ethical decision-making. While these materials have served primarily as face-to-face teaching aids. The aim is to make these resources more interactive, accessible, and suitable for both self-paced learning and trainer-facilitated sessions through OpenPlato and the Projects platform.

3.9.1 Content maintenance

Thematic Leaders (EARMA & AU) in collaboration with pilot organizations will jointly take responsibility for maintaining and expanding the Research Integrity training. EARMA supports a structured monitoring of new and relevant resources, references and documents, especially taking into considerations exploring synergies between other projects and programmes EARMA is or has been involved in: The iRECs project (2022-2025) that developed open accessible online trainings and resources integrated into the [ENERI classroom](#). RE4GREEN designed materials on research ethics and the green transition. [SOPs4RI](#) that developed an online, freely accessible and easy-to-use 'toolbox' supporting RPOs and RFOs cultivate research integrity and reduce detrimental practice and the [EARMA Academy](#) a dedicated learning hub designed to advance the professional development of the European research management and administration community. The material used for the research integrity course within PATTERN was reused and adapted for the EARMA Academy, specifically the open access online hub for Module 3 focusing on Research Ethics and Integrity. All courses are open access, free, and certified through EARMA. (link: [Online modules | Earma Academy](#)).

The Research Integrity materials have been reused and adapted for the EARMA Academy's open-access online hub, which will offer six modules: Introduction to Research Management; Funding Landscape and Proposal Development; Research Ethics and Integrity (Module 3); Open Science; Communication and Stakeholder

Engagement; and AI in Research Management. The hub is aligned with RMComp, spanning levels RM1 (Foundation) to RM3. All courses are open access and free, with optional certification through EARMA for a small fee — available either per module (e.g. Module 3) or for a full level (the RM1 package, with assessments across all six courses). Authors and reviewers are publicly credited. The Academy will be complemented by in-person workshops led by topic experts, and the EARMA mentorship scheme will be integrated in due course. Enquiries are handled via academy@earma.org and a dedicated contact form on the hub.

3.9.2 Case studies maintenance

To increase learner engagement and relevance, thematic leaders will support the integration of these materials on the Projects platform, enabling peer discussions and comment-based reflection. This approach aims to shift learners from passive understanding to applied reasoning, aligning closely with PATTERN's broader goals of experiential learning and cross-thematic coherence.

4 Institutional support

The long-term impact of PATTERN's training depends on institutions embedding these courses into their educational and operational frameworks. The institutional dimension of sustainability was examined in depth during the 2nd and 3rd Open Studio cycles and is documented in D4.3 (Second PATTERN Policy Brief). To avoid duplication, this section does not restate that analysis; it summarises only the points most directly tied to sustaining the training platform and modules and refers the reader to D4.3 for the full treatment.

4.1 Embedding Training and building institutional capacity

Sustaining PATTERN's training within institutions rests on integrating the courses into formal training activities — particularly for early-career researchers — with clear recognition such as credits, certifications, or digital badges, and embedding them in professional development frameworks via Human Resources. Adoption into regular curricula is what allows institutions to keep refining the materials without relying on project funding. This requires practical support: access to digital infrastructure and trainers, train-the-trainer resources, structured feedback mechanisms, and modular, flexible formats that institutions can adapt — including alignment with institutional regulations such as Gender Equality Plans. D4.3 details these measures and the supporting evidence.

4.2 Partnerships, engagement, and challenges

Universities and research organisations extend the reach of PATTERN training by linking academia, policy, civil society, and industry, and by promoting ORRI through familiar framings such as Open Science and research impact. Post-project viability depends on continued collaboration within the consortium — partners taking ownership of specific themes and committing to periodic updates — and beyond it, through synergies with NCPs, university associations, funders, thematic networks (e.g. GENDERACTION+, EOSC, EuroDoc), and sister projects such as COALESCE. Sustaining the modular, PBL-based methodology will require both human resources and community-maintained repositories (e.g. OpenPlato, REINFORCING). Embedding training into formal curricula still faces real obstacles — bureaucratic hurdles, gaps in internal expertise, and occasional resistance at senior level. PATTERN's responses (management-level advocacy, flexible formats, teacher support packages, and alignment with funders' requirements) are set out in full in D4.3.

5 Conclusions

This report builds directly on the sustainability framework set out in D2.3, which already detailed the multi-dimensional approach (technical, financial, content, and institutional) and the associated mitigation strategies. Rather than restating that analysis, D2.4 confirms and updates it in light of the second Open Studio cycle and the 2026 Brussels dedicated sustainability workshop.

The central conclusion has now been resolved: the partner institutions wish to continue using the platforms and building on the pedagogical resources but will not contribute dedicated budgets after the project ends. This is no longer an open question as it was in D2.3. Crucially, this does not threaten sustainability — LPI and OpenAIRE have each secured new grants and funding commitments that ensure both platforms (Projects and OpenPlato) remain open, maintained, and even expanded for at least five years.

The eight training courses remain available to all learners and trainers through decentralised stewardship by thematic leaders, under open licences, as described in Section 3. Institutional integration strategies are covered in Section 4 and, in more depth, in D4.3.

6 Additional information

Additional information has been discussed in-depth during PATTERN 2nd and 3rd Open Studio Cycles, held in March 2025 and April 2026 in the context of WP4 activities. Accordingly, many institutional support points have already been covered by [D4.3 Second PATTERN Policy Brief⁴](#) in order NOT to duplicate content.

6.1 List of meaningful differences with D2.3

The biggest change concerns the financial question that D2.3 left open — whether partners would fund the platforms once the project ends. That now has an answer, as explained in Executive Summary, Sections 2.3.6 and 2.6.3.

Since D2.3 we also held the third Open Studio (Brussels, 2026) and ran a partner consultation in April 2026, both of which fed into this version, including survey results on whether partners will keep updating courses and using the platforms (Section 3.1.1).

A few things that were "planned" in D2.3 have since actually happened. Zenodo is now used to reference all the major pedagogical resources, with proper versioning and attribution (Sections 3.1 and 3.1.1). And in several themes, partners are already reusing the materials rather than waiting for formal adoption — LPI is running an adapted Citizen Science training (3.2.1), SISSA is delivering Science Communication externally (3.3.1), APRE is looking at a paid version of its D&E course (3.4.1), and the Research Integrity content has been folded into the EARMA Academy (3.9.1).

We've also added real usage figures for OpenPlato — 59+ courses, 2,000+ active users, millions of interactions — which weren't available a year ago (Section 2.3.2).

Some courses changed in the details (Section 3): Citizen Science is now two modules (3.2), Open Access was trimmed from seven courses to four (3.7), FAIR RDM gained two self-paced courses (3.8), and GNI now has an asynchronous version on OpenPlato (3.5).

Smaller updates: LOBA joined LPI and OpenAIRE in committing to login-system maintenance (2.5.2); we flagged switching on self-service registration for the Projects portal (2.6.1); and we tightened Sections 4 and 6, pointing to D4.3 for the institutional detail and dropping the draft sponsorship agreement that was in D2.3's annex.

⁴ D4.3 is a project's deliverable which is still under approval of the EC at the time of writing this document

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